

PLAN OVERVIEW

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: 3D printed implants for magnetically/near-infrared light stimuli-responsive drug delivery (3DMAGIR)

Creator:Alba Martínez

Principal Investigator: Alberto Lopez Ortega

Data Manager: Alba Martinez

Affiliation: Universidad Pública de Navarra

Funder: European Commission

Template: Horizon Europe Template

Project abstract:

The 3DMAGIR project will take advantage of low-cost and easy manufacturing of the 3D printing technology to develop novel controllable and contactless magneto and opto activeimplants for nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) delivery. The contactless actuation is crucial to avoid the problems associated with the wired connections to the exterior, such as the risks of inflammation and infection and it prevents the need to include bulky batteries and electronics to generate the electrical impulses inside the body, which also drastically reduces the cost and invasiveness of the implant.

The data management plan (DMP) of the project is being developed taking into account the Open Science practices. The DMP is a living document, which will be updated as required.

ID: 168967

Start date: 30-06-2023

End date: 30-06-2025

Last modified: 11-02-2025

Grant number / URL: CNS2022-135787

3D PRINTED IMPLANTS FOR MAGNETICALLY/NEAR-INFRARED LIGHT STIMULI-RESPONSIVE DRUG DELIVERY (3DMAGIR)

DATA SUMMARY

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

No previous data has been reused.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Project data will include txt, doc, Html, opju and xls files

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Record, compare and process lab test data.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The project is expected to produce around 10 GBs of data

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The data generated are research outputs obtained from experiments, including raw data, results, negative results, processed data, methods and pictures

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The generated data can be used by other researchers to reproduce and validate the project findings

FAIR DATA

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Taking into account the Open Science practices, scientific data will be made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
To make data findable, it will be shared in one or many records or uploads (datasets), each dataset will be provided with a persistent DOI (digital object identifier).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Datasets will be provided with the metadata required by the employed repository. In any case, data will be described by normalized metadata standards and vocabularies (e.g. Zenodo uses JSON-schema for rich metadata and can export metadata to other standards such as Dublin Core, Zenodo also uses FAIR or open vocabularies including DataCite's Metadata Schema, Open Definition, FundRef, OpenAIRE).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

In any case, keywords will be provided in the dataset metadata to enhance discovery (as long as the repository allows it, e.g. zenodo allows that metadata).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Repositories that make metadata harvestable and indexable (searchable) will be chosen (e.g. Zenodo sends metadata to DataCite servers).

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

This information (whether temporary, permanent, open public, restricted or only available within the research team) will be properly posted making use of public repositories, e.g. general-purpose repositories as Zenodo. Trusted repositories will be preferred.

UPNA institutional repository (academica-e, <https://academica-e.unavarra.es/>) will be employed to share preprints compatible with the particular editorial requirements as well as open access papers. In fact, this institutional repository of UPNA uses national and international standards for the documents descriptors and complies with the interoperability protocol OAI-PMH (Open Access Initiative-Protocol for Metadata Harvesting); it is also collected by OPEN Aire (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe), meeting all its requirements and directives.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Considered repositories are free to use, specifically, academia-e is the institutional repository of the Principal Investigators University.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Chosen repositories can assign an identifier, but not all of them assign a DOI (e.g. Zenodo provides a doi, but academia-e assigns a specific url identifier).

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Provided no restriction linked to their exploitation and intellectual property potential, generated data will be analyzed and selected to be available in open repositories. Publication of papers in scientific journals will be made in Open Access

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Data linked to a publication of patent will be kept under embargo or restricted access. The dataset will be made open once the publication acceptance is confirmed by the editors or the patent (to prevent a conflict with other researchers that may use the data while the months long process of publication unfolds), or when the patent is granted.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Data made open will be free and easy to access in their repository. Access to restricted data can be freely asked to the dataset owner (the researcher who uploads the record to the repository) by email or by the messaging tools provided by each repository.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Data requests will be handled on a case by case basis by the dataset owner

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

If the identity of the person accessing the data is relevant, an institutional email address will be required. Since the project doesn't manage sensitive data, the identity of the persons accessing the data is not recorded.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee, as there is no personal or sensitive data involved.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

The metadata availability depends on the repository policy. E.g. in zenodo metadata is openly available and licensed under CC0 (public domain dedication), except the email addresses of contributors.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Data will remain available and findable as long as the repositories exist, which is expected to be a long term given the choice of trusted repositories. Metadata can remain available if the data isn't, as this information is harvested by search engines, or sent to metadata databases (depends on the repository, zenodo sends the metadata to DataCite servers).

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Documentation required to access or read the data will be included in the datasets, or linked between datasets, as a general rule datasets and folders will contain at least a readme.txt file explaining the data and how to read it and which software (if any) is required. Software won't be included in the datasets.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

To make data interoperable, standardized open formats will be preferred (see previous question about data formats).

2.3. Making data interoperable:

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

The project uses common terms; however, in case of using uncommon ontologies or vocabularies these will be explained in the dataset readme or the published method or appendix.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

Will your data include qualified references[1] to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

[1]A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Datasets will contain qualified references to other datasets or publications of the project as needed (particularly, methodologies used to obtain a dataset may be explained in detail in a publication, while a dataset may be linked to a particular publication).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

As a general rule datasets and folders will contain at least a readme.txt file with information required to re-use the data files (variable definitions, units of measurement, methodologies, software required), extensive methodologies may be explained in an open access publication which will be linked to the pertinent dataset.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Datasets and publications will be licensed under standard reuse licenses, a Creative Common CC BY licence will be preferably selected.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Since the data produced in the project (except any with legal or size restrictions) will be eventually made open in a repository under a reuse license, the datasets will be useable by third parties, partially during the project and especially some time after the end of the project.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The provenance of the data will be documented in the readme files and translated to standard metadata when the repository supports it (when applicable, information about other source datasets, origin organization and place of the data, issue date, kind of data creation/collection method).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

We will take into account the six dimensions of data quality are accuracy, completeness, integrity, validity, timeliness, and uniqueness.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Since personal/sensitive data or consent form aren't necessary, no special data security or ethics are required.

OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Other research outputs include physical prototypes and material samples.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Physical and biological research outputs can't be shared in the same way, and will be stored in the University Department for a few years, the Principal Investigators will consider any access or reuse request of physical items in a case by case basis.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

The cost of making data and other research outputs FAIR is considered negligible or can't be precisely calculated: Data is available online, while prototypes and material samples aren't specially bulky and don't require security.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

The costs of making research outputs FAIR are handled by the University and/or the repository sponsors

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The people responsible for data management in the project, based on their roles, and providing alternative persons to fill the roles if needed:

Project Director: Alberto López

Metadata Generator (includes uploading/owning the datasets/records in repositories): Alberto López y Alba Martínez

Data Collection/Analysis (includes laboratory staff and data generation via simulations): Alba Martínez

External data centers/archives/web services: Zenodo, UPNA academica-e.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Data will be preserved as long as the repositories exist, which is expected to be a long term given the choice of trusted repositories. Cost is negligible. Principal Investigators decide what data is kept (see FAIR principles above).

DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

During the course of research activities the data is stored on researchers laptops and computer hard drives, and backed up frequently to both external storage and cloud storage (the University provides Microsoft's One Drive cloud storage for free to its researchers), each researcher is responsible for their generated data at this point and must submit their data to Principal Investigators when asked. The data will be uploaded to long term storage (repositories) as previously detailed. Since personal or sensitive data isn't expected, no special data security is required.

ETHICS

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

There are no ethics or legal issues impacting data sharing, at the moment.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No personal data (or consent questionnaires) are required.

OTHER ISSUES

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Data management takes in mind Open Science practices (e.g. FAIR data, open access), as required by the funder.

PLANNED RESEARCH OUTPUTS

DATASET - "NANOPARTICLES CHARACTERIZATION"

This directory will contain datasets containing images and test results of nanoparticles synthesis and characterization.

PLANNED RESEARCH OUTPUT DETAILS

Title	DOI	Type	Release date	Access level	Repository (ies)	File size	License	Metadata standard	May contain sensitive data?	May contain PII?
Nanoparticles characterization	10.5281/zenodo.14850141	Dataset	-	Open	Zenodo	-	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No